

Curated Collections for Enduring HASS and Indigenous Data Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

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CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS	2
THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB	3
OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS	3
THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP	4
CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP	4
NEXT STEPS	10
APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES	11
APPENDIX 1: QUESTION REGISTER	26

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarises responses from the workshop held on 4th March 2025 to co-design an upcoming ARDC infrastructure project that aims to deliver a platform for enduring HASS collections, using established digital humanities software, which enables researchers to build and maintain collections without specialised technical support.

This project is part of the Community Data Lab, which fosters the development of tools, datasets and documentation that enable researchers to use data from galleries, libraries, museums, archives and other collections.

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. Since early 2024 we have been undergoing a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure. Co-designing infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders helps the ARDC to create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning new investment in digital research infrastructure for HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research data communities, as part of the [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

The HASS and Indigenous RDC began with the identification of opportunities to accelerate the impact of HASS and Indigenous research in the [2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap](#). The Australian Government Department of Education commissioned scoping studies to identify investment-ready programs, several of which formed the foundational activities of the HASS and Indigenous RDC.

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish

long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

The ARDC is currently delivering infrastructure in six focus areas, some of which builds upon foundational activities delivered during the first phase of the HASS and Indigenous RDC and some of which are new activities designed in collaboration with the research community. These are:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities
- The Language Data Commons of Australia
- Social Science Research Infrastructure Network
- Australian Internet Observatory
- Australian Creative Histories and Futures
- Connections

THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB

The Community Data Lab is an ongoing activity under the Connections focus area of the HASS and Indigenous RDC. Through the Community Data Lab the ARDC seeks to improve researchers' ability to utilise the data made available from galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM) and other collections. This activity provides tools, datasets and guidance that meet needs shared by researchers with different research problems from multiple disciplines. The outputs of the first phase of the Community Data Lab are now available for use by researchers.

During the delivery of this phase, the ARDC developed a set of principles for the design of sustainable HASS infrastructure, which are (in brief):

- A preference for “infrastructure at rest” over infrastructure which requires costly active support
- The separation of data from analytics
- Efficiency and flexibility of platform design
- Reusable code
- Open Source code and Open Access guidance documents

The ARDC is now in the process of developing Phase 2 of the Community Data Lab to expand this suite of data, tools and guidance materials.

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the

people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

We began Problem Identification in 2024, by calling openly for registrations of interest from partners who might be able to help us to design and deliver projects for the Community Data Lab. We targeted groups at universities that provide research software engineering and data analytics support to HASS researchers, because these groups have strong experience building solutions for researchers and exposure to a range of current researcher needs. We brought potential partners together for a series of roundtable discussions. Through these discussions we identified a set of possible projects which would each serve the needs of researchers from multiple disciplines across multiple research institutions, and which could be developed in line with the principles described above.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the open co-design workshop described below. The workshop was advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP

The proposed project aims to deliver a platform for enduring HASS collections, using established digital humanities software, which enables researchers to build and maintain collections without specialised technical support. This project is being developed in partnership with the Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney.

CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

The co-design workshop was held virtually on 4th March 2025. The workshop was open to all and was attended by 45 participants from 18 organisations. Organisations represented included 14 Australian universities, as well as government organisations and research infrastructure providers.

The workshop aimed to refine our understanding of the challenge, validate the problem statement and its impact, confirm the user base for the proposed solution, and gather feedback on the proposed solution’s features. Michael Lynch (Sydney Informatics Hub, The University of Sydney) presented on the challenge, which was summarised with the following problem statement:

“A common requirement for HASS and Indigenous research is the ability to make digital cultural collections available online. Bespoke solutions are

frequently short-lived due to maintenance demands. This makes it challenging for researchers to process, publish and maintain enduring collections of research consistent with FAIR principles.”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1. A question register was maintained throughout the workshop to capture questions and comments outside of the scope of the workshop activities - this can be found in Appendix 2.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

Have we described the problem correctly?

- Validity of the problem statement
 - Problem is well articulated. It would be really useful for my team. It would save us enormous time and hopefully money in setting up a public database of our research
 - Presenting curated collections online is a live problem for HASS researchers, and a solution supported by national infrastructure will be important.
- Usability
 - Solution needs to be easy for researchers without tech skills - need to be able to use it easily
- Sustainability, long-term accessibility and long-term storage
 - The problem is expressed clearly, but keeping things accessible in perpetuity is not specified.
 - Perhaps an acknowledgement of the need for a sustainability model to ensure longevity
 - Relation between this service and long-term storage needs to be made clear
 - A major part of this problem statement is continuity - not just projects being short lived - dependence on people
 - This issue goes hand in hand with long-term data storage, and so the problem statement identifies part of the problem. The data storage part also needs solving at national and local infrastructure levels
- Funding and cost concerns
 - A key component of the problem is the lack of ongoing funding for maintaining websites
 - Two nuances, the high cost of storage and costs of skilled personnel
 - There is more detail that I think crucial including financial/cost barriers both to data storage and to development of appropriate platforms
- Customisation and flexibility

- Perhaps being clearer about the value of balancing an enduring framework with a degree of customisation
- Indigenous data sovereignty
 - Shouldn't CARE principles get a mention?
 - The scope of the problem could extend beyond the statement - e.g., how to ensure indigenous data sovereignty within this framework etc

Who is this problem important to?

- Researchers and research support personnel
- Funding bodies
- Data custodians/data owners
- Students
- University institutions
- Project partners and collaborators
- General public
- Developers and software engineers
- Those who the research is relevant to
- Other significant groups including IT staff, archivists, GLAM sector

Would addressing this problem be valuable (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)

- Researchers can focus on research not technical tasks
 - Researchers should not be website builders, but users
 - Non-technical researchers will not have direct responsibility for ensuring the legacy accessibility of their research project's digital data
- Technical expertise
 - Make use of the expertise and resource from developers via different research domains
- Improved research
 - It would produce more quality research, more output. Less time spent on data collection efforts.
 - Knowledge maintenance within research teams would be improved
 - It would make digital research output much easier
- Sustainability and preservation
 - Addressing this problem would ensure preserving information for the future
 - Very valuable as research outputs and collections will be made available for the long term and future benefits and future researchers
 - Future Indigenous generations and others will be able to gain access to information that could otherwise be lost
- Visibility, access and dissemination

- It's valuable for meeting obligations to funding bodies and making data available to the public, when it has been gathered using public money
- If I had a platform to use, I would be able to make a database available to people anywhere in the world who were interested in Modern architecture in Australia and New Zealand
- Tools and standards
 - Academic libraries will be able to use stable platforms as a part of research data training and research support for the benefit of HDR students and researchers, and academic and teaching staff and students
 - Yes (addressing the problem is valuable), assuming that standards can be established and adopted to ensure preservation of the dataset.
- Other comments
 - Small effort for a very large result if this goes through
 - The DH community has been saying this for more than 10 years. It's good to see someone finally listening and something finally happening

**Activity 2: What HASS websites or data collections would you want to import into Omeka S?
Give specific examples**

- Types of data and formats
 - Data from interview, survey including text, video, audio and transcription, which might need annotation, mapping and data analysis functions
 - Audio-visual collections including sound files, video, time-aligned transcriptions that we would want to be able to present on a website alongside contextual descriptions, images and links out to other sites. As well as visualisations of data that might link to audio-visual recordings.
 - 40 years of paper data
- Interoperability
 - How do you connect to existing things like DiSSCO?
 - Important to get projects to engage early so that they can leverage interoperable data structures and transformation process can be minimised
 - Interoperability with TLCmap. Omeka S maps are too limited. Would be good to put TLCMap data in Omeka S to use linking and Multimedia in Omeka S
- Previous experiences with Omeka S or digital platforms
 - A comprehensive list of candidate sites for USyd FASS was generated in 2024 the Omeka S pilot project
 - Archive of audio and video and photos of Koori and Murri people talking about experiences in Missions and Reservers. We tried to implement it in Omeka S a year ago, but had to stop work before launch due to lack of ongoing maintenance and skills. We still have data, so would like to run up in this if possible
- Specific websites/data collections

- Opening the Multilingual Archive of Australia (OMAA)
- I have a collection of materials in the language that I research, going back over 150 years, together with images and links to artefacts
- <https://jewishmusicandtheatre.org>
- <https://manto.unh.edu/viewer.p/60/2616/scenario/1/geo/>
- <https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au>
- <https://aiatsis.gov.au/collection>
- <https://www.uq.edu.au/news/article/2024/08/securing-voices-of-country>
- <https://exhibitions.library.unsw.edu.au/performing-sydney>
- Collection management
 - I would like to see OmekaS running on a raspberry pi, with a simple way to get a set of RO-Crates as the source
 - We have struggled to develop an appropriate digital storage platform nor could we afford existing ones. This would be a combination of collection and LMS platform. Ideally, it could be visually as well as searchable by keywords
 - Lots of projects want a knowledge hub - may not have digital media or need to be imported. Can Omeka work for this?

Activity 3a: Who would be the viewers of an Omeka S based website for your research?

- Researchers and academics
- General public
- Government and policy makers
- Special groups including journalists, students, music lovers wanting to learn about unfamiliar music
- Community members and cultural groups
 - Indigenous community members and the wider community
 - Members of the communities (South Sudanese Australians) will be using the website. They have multiple languages and literacy levels. It will be a repository of their music and culture and where they can share and add to it
 - Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders wanting information about their own history and ancestors

3b. How would they interact with the website? Give examples of what they would use the information to achieve

- Data interaction and visualisation
 - The ability to play media together with transcripts, where transcripts are done in a standard format (like ELAN), and the relationship between the media and the transcript is made explicit
 - Visualisation tools as plugins (interactive charts)
- Viewing and searching collections

- Many researchers will just browse the website as it is, but APIs from programmatic access will be important. Search and discovery will be particularly valuable, especially semantic search
- Search by keywords, see visualisation or timeline/map
- Data access and restrictions
 - Sometimes there will need to be restricted access (e.g. for Indigenous Data Sovereignty)
 - For accessibility, websites need to be easy to navigate (for any audience)
- Technological features and integration
 - Integration with AI services for semantic and syntactic
 - Important for researchers to have analytics at the backend to get a sense of how many people are visiting the website/demonstrate engagement with the site
 - Connection to wikidata and other databases
 - Google indexing of individual pages is useful in many cases

During the discussion, it became evident that a number of audience members lacked familiarity with Omeka S. They sought further clarification on its capabilities, including its functionality, the extent to which it supports collaborative data input, and its accessibility for users without internet connectivity.

Activity 4: If you could export a website from Omeka-S to a standard RO-crate format, what would you do with the export? Again give specific examples

- Archiving and preservation
 - Upload it to a research data repository that provides some guarantee of longevity
 - Possibly for archival and preservation purposes. The RO-Crate object will be stored on institution preservation system
 - Store in Australian Data Archive if possible
 - We'd use one of the many other export formats that Omeka-S allows instead. We'd keep such an export as a backup. We'd publish it as a standalone archived dataset on figshare, periodically updating with newer versions and keeping the same DOI
- Sharing and making data accessible
 - Sharing the data collections with communities without internet access
 - Mount RO-Crate on national infrastructure so that search can be enabled across projects
- Data processing and research use
 - Search the metadata in the first instance to 'filter' for datasets that could potentially be of use
 - Use scripts to retrieve original data or perform data analysis
- Challenges with RO-Crate tools

- RO-Crate needs better tools for user interaction with the archive. Otherwise it remains a bit inscrutable to anyone but an IT person exporting and importing in the correct format
- Other comments
 - Kind of depends on what tooling is available for RO-Crate formatted data - and that's very much a moving target
 - Apart from Ro-Crate, we have used this archiving tool:
<https://webrecorder.net/browsertrix/>

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close end of day Friday 23 May. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2025.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line 'Curated Collections'.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES

Full text of workshop responses

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Have we described the problem correctly?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Problem is well articulated. Needs to be easy to use for non-tech people. It would be really useful for my team. It would save us enormous time and hopefully money in setting up a public database of our research. ● It might be important to refer to the need to balance 'enduring' collections with lifecycle management - ie forever' probably doesn't exist with digital. ● Perhaps being clearer about the value of balancing an enduring framework with a degree of customisation. ● key component of the problem is the lack of ongoing funding for maintaining websites ● Cost of maintenance once original staff member has left ● Shouldn't CARE principles get a mention? ● Perhaps an acknowledgement of the need for a sustainability model to ensure longevity ● also need to make it sustainable for both the researchers and organisations. ● Two nuances: 1. high cost of storage is a problem 2. skills and people costs ● The problem is expressed clearly, but keeping things accessible in perpetuity is not specified. ● (The problem is expressed clearly, but keeping things accessible in perpetuity is not specified.) "collections available online,... accessible long-term." (is this a better re-wording?) ● This problem comes hand in hand with the problem of maintaining accessibility of this data for a significant period of time and, simultaneously, the tools required to work with it ● Relation between this service and long-term storage needs to be made clear ● Missing- centralised models, entry info, standard config - not ust Omeka-S is being offered, but that it is offered with centralised skills and examples support ● Yes ● Yes ● Solution needs to be easy for researchers without tech skills - need to be able to use it easily ● Must include examples and what is possible. There is not existing an easy example to understand ● Some researchers haven't learnt the vocabulary they do not need to know. This lets them participate ● Yes, although the scope of the problem could extend beyond the statement - e.g., how to ensure indigenous data sovereignty within this framework etc

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The digital paradigm for a significant proportion of humanities project can be abstracted as ‘relationship graphing’. These projects are characterised as incremental, cumulative, granular, and collaborative semantic annotation and linking of heterogenous content and data. Rather than follow a research paradigm of repeatable experiments (text set-algorithm-result set) the research output is a node graph and a persistent web presence. ● Presenting curated collections online is a live problem for HASS researchers, and a solution supported by national infrastructure will be important. This issue goes hand in hand with long-term data storage, and so the problem statement identifies part of the problem. The data storage part also needs solving at national and local infrastructure levels. ● Main concerns: longevity (how to maintain the website after the project / funding ends), ability to embed music and videos, ability to continually add content from community members, searchability, shareability, etc. ● ensuring website still exists when a researcher moves to a different uni – transferrable and ensuring that the website is still publicly available and useable after funding has finished ● Yes ● Yes, although there is more detail that I think crucial including financial/cost barriers both to data storage and to development of appropriate platforms. ● Yes ● Yes, but there are also issues around sharing or not sharing cultural data. ● It isn't just maintenance, but the cost of the work and the skills required. ● A major part of this problem statement is continuity - not just projects being short lived - dependence on people ● Undocumented dependencies, hard to fix if you know what they are ● Portability of skills to work on another research project ● Staff/skills continuity ● In 'maintenance' include lack of staff skills and knowledge continuity. As we are casualised, someone who could fix maintenance issue in 5 minutes is not available. Meaning weeks and months, of finding and onboarding another staff member to fix tiny glitches. ● Available online should cover access by unskilled users as well as sophisticated API access to facilitate involvement of data owners. ● add consistency to the wording - consistency enables researchers to add to their own capability, and for an expectation of experience (for users and developers) ● customising the collection manage system or research tools are complicated too as different projects have different need and requirements, even using tools like Omeka S which has much focus on record metadata and media data ● The starting point was a problem (lack of sustainable access to research results). What we are looking at is really moving that problem: instead of individuals or groups being responsible, we are aiming for someone (ARDC) to provide an ongoing service provided
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	<p>data/metadata is , made available in certain formats.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • and ensuring that the website is still publicly available and useable after funding has finished • You're missing the other side of the coin when it comes to digital cultural collections - the project web presence (e.g. the "About Us" page, Contact page, Contribute page, context about the collection page, etc. Not just publishing a dataset)
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QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Who is the problem important to?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers, and the external people/organisations they collaborate with. Eg a website that draws on researcher's work but is useful for a museum's public • Funding bodies -- being able to show a sustainable future for the work • Projects with multiple partners • The data owners need to be involved, not just researchers. +1 • (The data owners need to be involved, not just researchers. +1) The data owner need to be established clearly. Usually it is the institution and funders. • people/public who need the relevant data • The problem is important to researchers, to government, to students and to the public who might have an interest. • Barrier to participation of people without digital skills set - but who are excellent researchers • teams who currently do this work because no-one else has responsibility • project partners • universities paying for staff who do this work (because they can) but are not responsible for it • any researcher with a hope for making their research available for others to see and reuse • Very Important as research grant lifetimes are often not long enough to sustain outputs - this matters to researchers involved, funders, research participants and community as a whole - now and in the future, • researchers, custodians, the general public • Can be a big difference between a basic archive and something for general use that needs to look great and have good functionality • The people the research is relevant to • people that want to know about the subject of each collection - general public • software engineers maintaining these things - one standard platform nationally available makes the effort much more effective! +1 • Developers who make tools for analysing the collections need consistent and reliable access in the long run, so the same tool can be reused on other collections and still stay useful in a few years or longer future. • Researcher skillset is different to website maintenance skillset

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researchers, developers, industry specialists. large and small, businesses, students at different levels and project managers ● All researchers of all stages +1 ● researchers are skilled at what they do - they shouldn't have to be website experts for their work to have impact ● interesting projects from PHD or Master students ● It is worth looking at how the French govt. has provided for long term data curation in Humanum. https://www.huma-num.fr/presentation/, https://www.huma-num.fr/presentation/, https://www.huma-num.fr/presentation/ ● Indigenous communities ● Need for vocabulary bridges and entry points guided clearly by resources ● Researchers wanting reproducibility, citability and longevity for all their hard work. 3rd space workers and IT staff wanting their work recognised as 'publications' / NTOs so they can get out of the casualisation spiral and build a career. Researchers who want to use existing research instead of having to redo all the work. ● experience has shown that there is a high demand for creating supported research websites from people all across the university ● It's important to large numbers of HASS researchers, who have obligations to funders to make curated data available, but don't have the tools and technical solutions to enable this. These researchers need support from their institutions to use any technical solutions and to maintain and update them for the long term. ● people wanting to share their research ● Researcher, data owner, funders and curators/archivists ● Academic researchers, students, the public who are interested in particular topics, industry, government -- the list is long and it depends on the area. ● Researchers, GLAM sector, Policy researchers, owners of data ● Anyone who promises a searchable online database in the data management section of ARC applications... which is everyone who does those applications!
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QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Would addressing this problem be valuable? (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Researchers in humanities and social sciences who would not need to spend time / develop expertise finding the optimal solution ● " ● long term study stronger results for policy and humanities research ● Knowledge maintenance within research teams would be improved ● It would produce more quality research, more output. Less time spent on data collection efforts. ● There would be more visibility for non traditional research +1 ● Yes, addressing this problem would ensure preserving information for the future. ● make digital research output much easier ● Academic libraries will be able to use stable platforms as a part of research data training and research support for the benefit of HDR students and researchers, and academic and teaching staff and students. ● It would support universities to provide platforms for researchers to share their data in accessible ways ● Yes! non-technical researchers will not have to have direct responsibility for ensuring the legacy accessibility of their research project's digital data ● Help reach broader audience than traditional media and make information generally accessible ● Valuable provided there is policy to ensure tools are used consistently ● Yes! I could move my project beyond a good idea to a research project with a public outcome/value ie for a museum ● Very valuable as research outputs and collections will be made available for the long term and future benefits and future researchers ● Yes, but needs to be embedded in documentation that points users to a range of options (including this one) according to their specific needs ● Yes, assuming that standards can be established and adopted to ensure preservation of the dataset. ● Yes, at least standards are established, at most, there will be a national service available. ● Researchers should not be website builders, but users ● (Researchers should not be website builders, but users) researchers should not have to be website builders ● Would also enhance more traditional library collections. ● Future Indigenous generations and others will be able to gain access to information that could otherwise be lost. ● It's valuable for meeting obligations to funding bodies and making data available to the public, when it has been gathered using public money. ● Small effort for a very large result if this goes through ● Researchers without skills want assistants from people with skills. People with those skills working with researchers want a job (not 5 parts of jobs with different employers all at once or in a row) and be paid for work. Nobody has been willing to create such jobs till recently. I hope this helps solve this part of the problem.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes it would be. If I had a platform to use I would be able to make a database available to people anywhere in the world who were interested in Modern architecture in Australia and New Zealand. The subject is under researched and there is no good comprehensive study or resource at the moment. ● take up of shared software by multiple groups ie Unis and GLAM ● This would allow skills support staff in Universities to focus on other areas ● A common data access API would speed the development of portals and other applications. ● Yes, as well as the managed Omeka-S service, I think the package of templates and tools developed would be very useful to those using Omeka-S in other contexts (self hosting etc). ● make use of the expertise and resource from developers via different research domains ● Yes, addressing this would be valuable but needs to be seen as part of a continuum including other modes of digital dissemination e.g. online journals, possibilities we have not yet thought of. ● Yes, but given Omeka-S exposes LOD, will identifiers for entities persist across the live and static versions? ● Yes. The DH community has been saying this for more than 10 years. It's good to see someone finally listening and something finally happening. ● longitudinal and distant visions research, a continuum that would allow Humanities researchers to see their subjects differently. It is potentially very empowering for informing policy research, ideally if taken up by researchers, GLAM partners and government as policy the partnerships could be stronger ● Omeka-S can be harvested by National Library's Trove platform. Items appearing in trove searches would be amazing.
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Activity 2

QUESTION	RESPONSES
What HASS websites or data collections would you want to import into Omeka S? Give specific examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● data from interview, survey including text, video, audio and transcription, which might need annotation, mapping and data analysis functions as well ● Audio-visual collections including sound files, video, time-aligned transcriptions that we would want to be able to present on a website alongside contextual descriptions, images and links out to other sites. As well as visualisations of data that might link to audio-visual recordings. Some examples of recent sites created that we would want to import: https://www.hearingthemusic.info/ https://www.reclaimingperformance.info https://gudjal.au/ https://angke.kaytetye.com.au/stories/daisy/. https://kaytetye.com.au/,https://www.hearingthemusic.info/, https://www.hearingthemusic.info/ https://www.reclaimingperformance.info/,

	<p> https://www.reclaimingperformance.info, https://gudjal.au/, https://gudjal.au/</p><p><a> https://angke.kaytetye.com.au/stories/daisy/, https://angke.kaytetye.com.au/stories/daisy/,
 https://kaytetye.com.au/, https://kaytetye.com.au/</p> </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An LOD resource for Greek myth I co-direct, currently in Nodegoat, includes ancient artefacts held in Australian and NZ collections: https://manto.unh.edu/viewer.p/60/2616/scenario/1/geo/,https://manto.unh.edu/viewer.p/60/2616/scenario/1/geo/, https://manto.unh.edu/viewer.p/60/2616/scenario/1/geo/</p> • 40 years of paper data - needs inputting to any database - around 10-15 years to input set aside • https://jewishmusicandtheatre.org/ This is a site that was constructed for an AHRC project I was involved with. Badly managed by ULeeds.,https://jewishmusicandtheatre.org/, https://jewishmusicandtheatre.org/ +1 • Interactive site to visualise certain works.(HTML, CSS, and Javascript) • Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia: https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au,https://www.chia.chinese museum.com.au • No useful for earth and environment • https://aiatsis.gov.au/collection • (https://aiatsis.gov.au/collection) But which parts of the collections? • https://www.uq.edu.au/news/article/2024/08/securing-voices-of-country • this is a difficult question to answer without an understanding of what Omeka S CAN actually do - a better question might have been 'what materials do you want to share' and what kind of connection do you want between them, and what functionality do you want for the website (eg. access restrictions) • Opening the Multilingual Archive of Australia (OMAA) +1 • https://aiatsis.gov.au/research/languages/national-indigenous-languages-surveys • How does Omeka S relate to DISSCO in the EU? • ausstage +2 • (ausstage) or being able to connect to Ausstage at least, pull data from there • GLAM sector catalogues • performing sydney https://exhibitions.library.unsw.edu.au/performing-sydney +1 • Our project is an ARC project which is a comparative study of the music in China and Australia (South Sudanese); non-mainstream groups The website is mainly for sharing music within the communities which have multiple languages and different literacy levels. Site content - very visual, not too much texts, mainly music, photos, videos, visualizations, undergrad projects (e.g., collection of songs in collaboration with the community) Main concerns: longevity (how to maintain the website after the project / funding ends), ability to embed music and videos, ability to continually add content from community members, searchability, shareability, etc. • Collections of 3d models - archaeology, natural history, 3d scans of
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	<p>architecture, plants, object. Examples below: https://sea.pedestal3d.com/r/UifoHrMoMH https://natural.austmus.pedestal3d.com/r/BMRXcfijnx/ https://artsunit-doensw.pedestal3d.com/r/HKLSjlnrt_ https://crarm.pedestal3d.com/gallery/ https://texstyle-exhibition.com.au/2024/projects/ https://virtual.kings.edu.au/collection/overview_burns_family_cemetery/, https://sea.pedestal3d.com/r/UifoHrMoMH, https://sea.pedestal3d.com/r/UifoHrMoMH, https://natural.austmus.pedestal3d.com/r/BMRXcfijnx/, https://natural.austmus.pedestal3d.com/r/BMRXcfijnx/, https://natural.austmus.pedestal3d.com/r/BMRXcfijnx/, https://artsunit-doensw.pedestal3d.com/r/HKLSjlnrt_, https://artsunit-doensw.pedestal3d.com/r/HKLSjlnrt_, https://artsunit-doensw.pedestal3d.com/r/HKLSjlnrt_, https://crarm.pedestal3d.com/gallery/, https://crarm.pedestal3d.com/gallery/, https://crarm.pedestal3d.com/gallery/, https://texstyle-exhibition.com.au/2024/projects/, https://texstyle-exhibition.com.au/2024/projects/, https://texstyle-exhibition.com.au/2024/projects/, https://virtual.kings.edu.au/collection/overview_burns_family_cemetery/, https://virtual.kings.edu.au/collection/overview_burns_family_cemetery/, https://virtual.kings.edu.au/collection/overview_burns_family_cemetery/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● https://transdisciplinary-research-science.sydney.edu.au/home/online-teaching-and-learning-resources/campusflora/ ● https://transdisciplinary-research-science.sydney.edu.au/home/our-research/digitising-haswells-historic-zoological-collection/ ● Large Images (JPEG2000/TIFF), video files, or interactive website. ● Specific websites ● How do you connect to existing things like DiSSCO (https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article/72/10/978/6648186) ● Collection plus Learning Management System - teaching materials for student ● OHRM outputs that are now in ROCrate +1 ● important to get projects to engage early so that they can leverage interoperable data structures and transformation process can be minimised ● Interoperability with TLCmap. Omeka S maps are too limited. Would be good to put TLCMap data in Omeka S to use linking and Multimedia in Omeka S ● program evaluation data collected by govt (but what can or cannot be shared?) ● The international project, The Modernism Collective, is assembling data on architecture projects in Australia and New Zealand that includes photographs, drawings, histories, links to readings, links to other websites, walking tours, teaching guides, and more. We have struggled to develop an appropriate digital storage platform nor could we afford existing ones. This would be a combination of collection and LMS platform. Ideally, it could be visually as well as searchable by key words. ● I am working on the diary of an early 19thC German actress. I'd like to be able to include a facsimile of her diary for readers to flip through, a translation (into English), plus links from, eg, people and places
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	<p>mentioned to images, paintings, maps etc of those things/people. Also documents associated with that actress: letters to/from her (and links to further info about the writers), contracts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A comprehensive list of candidate sites for USyd FASS was generated in 2024 the Omekas S pilot project +1 ● Archive of audio and video and photos of Koori and Murri people talking about experiences in Missions and Reservers. We tried to implement in Omeka S year ago, but had to stop work before launch due to lack of ongoing maintenance and skills. We still have data, so would like to run up in this if possible, if there's funding to pay someone to work on ingest and finishing linking records. ● I have a collection of materials in the language that I research, going back over 150 years, together with images and links to artefacts and would like to present this in an attractive format (currently an html page) +1 ● Indigenous collections from the museums and communities (repatriation from the museums etc). Video archive for performance. Mapping collection for historical data etc. ● Lots of projects want a knowledge hub - may not have digital media or need to be imported. Can Omeka work for this? ● I would like to import and grow the Modernism Collective's work on cataloguing important architecture in Australia and New Zealand. We would combine with Docomomo's collection, the Architecture Museum at UniSA, and more. ● A preliminary analysis of 2024 and 2025 ARC projects across relevant FOR codes disclosed a likely requirement for a CMS solution (of the nature of that being proposed) in as many approximately 55% of projects. ● This would be a priority for FASS - migrating important projects ● I would like to see OmekaS running on a raspberry pi, with a simple way to get a set of ROCrates as the source ● Collections yet to be collected - i.e., future projects that can work towards this capacity. ● Database including a new catalogue of a composer's works, linked to names, dates, places, archival documents, facsimile manuscripts, recordings, images etc. and showing networks of connections between them, e.g. where was an opera performed, who were the singers, set designer, music director etc; what other performances did those individuals do? when and where else did they collaborate? Where is the score that they performed from and who was the copyist? etc. etc. What recordings have been made and where can they be accessed? ● relational type database sharing details/connections of historical figures/communities +1 ● How do you link to existing systems such as DiSSCo (https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article/72/10/978/66481860)
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Activity 3

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Who would be the viewers of an Omeka S based website for your research and how would they interact with the website? Give examples of what they would use the information to achieve</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Viewers would be other researchers, the general public, community members engaging with personal cultural histories. They would view materials, read stories, listen to audio-visual examples, follow transcripts along with audio or video, and follow links out to more detailed information on other sites (e.g. on Trove or in other databases such as PARADISEC) or links to the full research (journal articles etc.) ● For general interest, specific disciplinary interest, for citation in academic articles, for reference and direction in non-academic articles ● journalists ● Potential collaborators ● Two audiences: one is theatre historians/Goethe scholars/academics, accessing the site through a Goethe Museum. The second audience would be a general public audience, visiting the museum who could interact with the website (and possibly some of the actual objects) during a visit to the museum. That is, the Omeka S site would need to be accessible via another organisation's website ● students and other researchers accessing the data that has been collected for their own research ● Reviewer. Depending on the use the reviewer can be the repository reviewer, funder, etc ● academic interest ● Can it be accessed mobily? ● I'm not sure what the audience for this kind of communication is meant to be. If I want the full-on research results, I'll be looking for publications via a library of other search possibility. If I want to see the underlying data, I'll be looking in other places. I can see that there may be a general interest audience, but that will vary in size enormously across different areas of research, but I'm still left wondering about whether there is value here to the scholarly community. ● (I'm not sure what the audience for this kind of communication is meant to be. If I want the full-on research results, I'll be looking for publications via a library of other search possibility. If I want to see the underlying data, I'll be looking in other places. I can see that there may be a general interest audience, but that will vary in size enormously across different areas of research, but I'm still left wondering about whether there is value here to the scholarly community.) Many researchers will just browse the website as it is, but APIs from programmatic access will be important. Search and discovery will be particularly valuable, especially semantic search. ● government agencies ● First Nations people ● Other researchers in the field (musicology). Performers looking for new repertoire or information about pieces they are playing. Music lovers generally, wanting to learn about unfamiliar music.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● will Omeka allow collaborators input the data? ● (will Omeka allow collaborators input the data?) Whoever creates the collection will be able to choose if they want to allow contributors or not ● Viewers would be architecture students and academics, architecture researchers, general public interested in architecture, government employees working on preservation and planning. They would use our Modernism Collective site for research, teaching, decisions about heritage conservation, decisions about planning even zoning. Other viewers could include tv producers looking for sites for tv programs and films. Viewers could include journalists. ● Other researchers, general public, community members. Search research or general information, search by keywords, see visualisation or timeline/map. Find top most popular books in the library etc ● Can it be accessed if people do not have internet - portable versions taken to remote users ● (Can it be accessed if people do not have internet - portable versions taken to remote users) Should be possible - see work PARADISEC have done delivering content to remote communities using Raspberry Pi as local server. The archival format we envisage should be easy to use for this purpose and accessible. Of course deploying a collection to a local server is also possible ● Researchers of the future who may have different perspectives and different ways of using the data as new tools developed and ideas grow. ● Indigenous community members and the wider community. Interaction. May interact with website to find out more about history and help to form a sense of self. ● Students who may learn more effectively by interacting with the data ● govt viewers ● Members of the communities (South Sudanese Australians) will be using the website. They have multiple languages and literacy levels. It will be a repository of their music and culture and where they can share and add to it. So it should be more visual and easy to use and maintain ● Researchers globally who will want to search for groups and individual items, perhaps undertake diachronic and geographically distributed analyses ● Researchers wanting to know what tools are available for a particular research method and visa versa ● I can imagine a small cultural agency, like an oral history society or local museum, creating a list of their collections using Crate-O or even OmekaS, but exporting to ROcrate ● People (general public) interested to learn about the stories presented ● Government policymakers - looking at historical narrative to avoid the mistakes of the past ● People in our discussion need more info about what Omeka S is,
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	<p>and whether it's been considered/selected in relation to other platforms and standards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Other academics and research students - to understand and contribute to the collections ● General public and politicians wanting to reliable information on a contentious topic. People wanting to self educate themselves on what they weren't taught at school. Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders wanting information about their own history and ancestors. School and Uni students researching assignments. Activists and advocates wanting 'ammunition'. Other researchers. +1 ● citizen scientists contributing their own crowdsourced contributions (perhaps researcher-moderated) ● There is a bit of 'mission creep' in some of these responses - what can Omeka S actually do? ● (There is a bit of 'mission creep' in some of these responses - what can Omeka S actually do?) There's a good plugin architecture, so this project could extend functionality if required. ● By funder, other researchers, publisher, assessor or repository manager. ● Academics, students, practicing architects, heritage conservation experts, city and regional planners, interested lay people. librarians -- are all potential users. They would interact with the website we imagine to do research on individual buildings, on architects, on types of architecture, on design approaches, etc. ● Everyone from family historians to real historians. Advanced search of collections. But also read more blog-post style pages that highlight themes in the collection and link to individual items. Probably browse collections via a map interface. ● visualisations - network charts, interactive bubble charts ● The ability to play media together with transcripts, where transcripts are done in a standard format (like ELAN) , and the relationship between the media and the transcript is made explicit ● Visualisation tools as plugins (interactive charts) ● (Viewers would be other researchers, the general public, community members engaging with personal cultural histories. They would view materials, read stories, listen to audio-visual examples, follow transcripts along with audio or video, and follow links out to more detailed information on other sites (e.g. on Trove or in other databases such as PARADISEC) or links to the full research (journal articles etc.)) There's a transcript follow-along plug in here: https://github.com/arepr/omeka-s-module-transcript we'll have to look further into if it works well or not. ● Atemporal non-formal publication ● Sometimes there will need to be restricted access (e.g. for Indigenous Data Sovereignty) ● Preliminary analysis of ARC 2024 and 2025 projects exposed that of those that might require a CMS most all would have 'researcher audience' as many as 20% of indicated the general public as an audience. ● narrative storytellers and content creators - through blogposts,
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	<p>videos, social media, non-fiction books, documentaries. They would interact with collections they are interested in the same as the general public - to view and search the collection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Visualisations - node graphs, mapping, generous archives ● Integration with AI services for semantic and syntactic ● Access requirements would really depend on the types of data available and for what purpose ● important for researchers to have analytics at the backend to get a sense of how many people are visiting the website/demonstrate engagement with the site ● access, what the restrictions and who can access them, access online ● it would be good to give example to users about how they can use the data and information, create other digital output by using the data provided on the site, or create new data, API and scripts to use exported data might be useful here. ● connection to wikidata and other databases ● For accessibility, websites need to be easy to navigate (for any audience) ● Quick interactivity for data experimenting ● glam sector may link to relevant collections see more about this here: ● Share and link between sites and entities using linked open data ● (Visualisation tools as plugins (interactive charts)) Does Omeka S allow this? ● Vocabularies for a range of contexts ● Google indexing of individual pages is useful in many cases ● (I'm not sure what the audience for this kind of communication is meant to be. If I want the full-on research results, I'll be looking for publications via a library of other search possibility. If I want to see the underlying data, I'll be looking in other places. I can see that there may be a general interest audience, but that will vary in size enormously across different areas of research, but I'm still left wondering about whether there is value here to the scholarly community.) Many researchers will just browse the website as it is, but APIs from programmatic access will be important. Search and discovery will be particularly valuable, especially semantic search.) We want the collections to be available via API as well under the same access restrictions as the public interface for each collection
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Activity 4

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>If you could export a website from Omeka-S to a standard RO-crate format, what would you do with the export? Again give specific examples</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research Object (RO) Crate = archival format that encapsulates data with its metadata and links. ● What is RO Crate? ● Possibly for archival and preservation purpose. The RO-Crate object will be stored on institution preservation system. +1 ● Out of my depth here... sorry - would like to contribute...! ● No idea. Can you express the question in plain English?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● use it for archiving purpose, use scripts to retrieve original data or perform data analysis ● Not a researcher question ● Upload it to a research data repository that provides some guarantee of longevity. +4 ● (Upload it to a research data repository that provides some guarantee of longevity. +4) I wonder about workflow here... My first idea would be that preparing data for long-term would have higher priority, making the collection to be shown via Omeka would be a side benefit of that process. ● We want this archival format to be static but also with an easy-to-navigate simple interface so that this format will guard against any platform no longer being supported ● For migration and for archiving/preservation. ● We'd use one of the many other export formats that Omeka-S allows instead. We'd keep such an export as a backup. We'd publish it as a standalone archived dataset on figshare, periodically updating with newer versions and keeping the same doi. ● Sharing the data collections with communities without internet access. ● Kind of depends on what tooling is available for RO-Crate formatted data - and that's very much a moving target. ● Mount RO-Crate on national infrastructure so that search can be enabled across projects ● Search the metadata in the first instance to 'filter' for datasets that could potentially be of use ● Process or analyse or combine the data and info in other systems or programs/websites, to do things not in Omeka S, do further research etc. ● For MANTO (https://manto.unh.edu/viewer.p/60/2616/scenario/1/geo/) Currently we publish completed subsets of data on Zenodo, with data dictionaries. We are working to create auto data dumps of the whole dataset regularly, again probably to Zenodo. Likely this could be done in an RO crate.,https://manto.unh.edu/viewer.p/60/2616/scenario/1/geo/, https://manto.unh.edu/viewer.p/60/2616/scenario/1/geo/ ● export to a static site (eg for taking to places where there is no/low internet) ● Apart from Ro-Crate, we have used this archiving tool : https://webrecorder.net/browsertrix/,https://webrecorder.net/browsertrix/, https://webrecorder.net/browsertrix/ ● ROCrate needs better tools for user interaction with the archive. For user to manually CRUD an ROCrate. Otherwise it remains a bit inscrutable to anyone but IT person exporting and importing in correct format. BUT it is important user can just unzip and click the HTML file. ● Variable fidelity of the export of structure, webpages, datasets, resources. comments ● Store in PARADISEC if possible
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Store in Australian Data Archive if possible +2● How do you link to existing systems such as DiSSCo (https://academic.oup.com/bioscience/article/72/10/978/66481860)
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APPENDIX 1: QUESTION REGISTER

(Anonymised)

Question	Response
Are there any questions about the approaches to meeting specific needs that have been outlined today?	
Are there any questions about the overall infrastructure development?	
It wasn't clear if Omeka S would be supported centrally (through ARDC) or if this is designing a methodology that others would follow (and self-resource) ?	Centrally managed platform running on Nectar. Users (Researchers) will create their project and add to it themselves. The template we use will be available but users are not required to self-deploy as the platform on nectar will be the way we expect researchers to use this.
Any other questions?	
Have any particular data sets/tooling/sizes or formats created a challenge for Omeka S?	Omeka deals with most of the formats we've seen and there's an extensive plugin library for even more. We don't anticipate problems here in the duration of the project.
Are there levels of access/access controls to downloads (thinking in terms of IDS)?	Default options in Omeka S are that material in your collection is either private and therefore only accessible by members of the project (researchers and their collaborators) or published and therefore public. There is an "Access" plugin that allows for more fine-grained control e.g. only users who are logged in (but not necessarily members of the project) can see things, or specific users or group of users.